

THE APPLICATION OF THE MODIFIED HASHIN'S FAILURE CRITERION AND 2D SOLID FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS TO THICK COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

J. C. Hall & G. F. Leon, General Dynamics/Electric Boat Division,
R. J. Nuismer, Hercules Composite Structures

ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the physically based composite material failure criterion put forth by Hashin and modified by Nuismer, and its application to thick composites and finite element analysis. Hashin proposed that failure of composite materials can be separated into two modes of failure: fiber failure (tension or compression) and matrix failure. The equations governing these modes of failure are presented. This failure criterion is applied to a couple of test specimens modeled with ABAQUS 2D solid finite elements. Numerous factors are shown to influence the failure predictions: the mesh size, the critical length, the smearing of material properties, and the material allowables.

Keywords: Composite Failure, Thick Composites, Material Allowables, Cylinders, Finite Element Analysis, In-Situ Consolidation

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Conventional composite material failure criteria, such as maximum stress, maximum strain, Tsai-Wu, etc., perform well for thin autoclave cured composites where the composite is subjected to membrane loading and the design allowables are established based upon extensive testing using flat coupon specimens. As thicker and thicker composite structures are designed, and these structures are subjected to extensive bending, compression or significant stress risers, a 3D failure criterion is required to investigate material failure and subsequent structural failure. In addition, if the structure has significant curvature, the reliability of using flat coupon test data to establish material allowables is highly questionable. Although the failure criterion to be discussed is applicable to any type of composite structure and loading, the discussion centers on its applicability to thick composite cylinders subjected to hydrostatic compression. In the ensuing discussion the failure criterion equations are reviewed, followed by the material allowables, stress analysis and sample problems.

2.0 FAILURE CRITERION

2.1 Lamina (Ply) Failure

The interactive failure criterion suggested by Hashin (Reference 1) divides failure of a lamina into two modes: fiber failure and matrix failure (Figure 1). The prediction of fiber failure in a lamina is based upon the calculation of the fiber direction stress or strain (σ_1 or ϵ_1), which is then compared to the tensile or compressive fiber allowable (Equation 1). Hashin's equations have been modified to include shear interaction with regards to fiber compressive stress.

$$\sigma_1 = \sigma_{1ta} \quad \text{for} \quad \sigma_1 > 0 \quad (1a)$$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_{1ca}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}^2 + \tau_{13}^2}{\tau_{12sa}^2}\right) = 1 \quad \text{for} \quad \sigma_1 < 0 \quad (1b)$$

Since matrix failure in a lamina is driven to occur along a plane parallel to the fiber direction, the prediction of matrix failure is based on the calculation of stresses acting on planes parallel to the fiber direction. Describing such a plane by the angle beta, as shown in Figure 2, the normal and shear stresses acting on the plane, in terms of the stresses acting on the lamina, are given by:

$$\sigma_n = \left(\frac{\sigma_2 + \sigma_3}{2}\right) + \left(\frac{\sigma_2 - \sigma_3}{2}\right)\cos 2\beta + \tau_{23}\sin 2\beta \quad (2a)$$

$$\tau_{nl} = -\left(\frac{\sigma_2 - \sigma_3}{2}\right)\sin 2\beta + \tau_{23}\cos 2\beta \quad (2b)$$

$$\tau_{nl} = \tau_{13}\sin\beta + \tau_{12}\cos\beta \quad (2c)$$

Failure of the matrix along the plane B is predicted to occur when the stresses on any plane first exceed an interactive combination of normal tension and shear, as expressed by the equations:

$$F_t = \left(\frac{\sigma_n}{\sigma_{2ta}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{nl}}{\tau_{23sa}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{nl}}{\tau_{12sa}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad \text{for} \quad \sigma_n > 0 \quad (3a)$$

$$F_c = \left(\frac{\sigma_{nl}}{\tau_{23sa}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{nl}}{\tau_{12sa}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad \text{for} \quad \sigma_n < 0 \quad (3b)$$

In the above equations, the numerators are the stresses applied to the lamina, while the denominators are the unidirectional lamina allowables. When $F_t = 1$, failure is predicted to occur from a combination of tension and shear. When $F_c = 1$, failure is predicted to occur from shear interaction. Matrix failure is predicted to occur where either of these equations is first satisfied. A closed form equation to determine the lamina stresses and surface for which lamina failure first occurs has not been found. However, a simple computer program is written to numerically determine the β angle at which F_t or F_c are a maximum.

2.2 Laminate Failure

Lamina failure does not necessarily translate into laminate failure, and numerous approaches have been derived to predict laminate failure, from first ply failure to progressive lamina failure. For the present discussion, lamina failure is equated to laminate failure, because the primary form of loading is compressive in nature, where failure is typically catastrophic for composites.

2.3 Stress Concentrations and Bending Effects

Unlike thin composite structures which are subjected to primarily membrane loading, thick composite structures, such as stiffened cylinders, can exhibit numerous through-the-thickness stress concentrations and large stress gradients due to bending and structural interfaces. Under such conditions, stress concentrations can be accounted for by the stress averaging approach introduced by Whitney and Nuismer (Reference 2). Application of this methodology to each critical area of the structure is accomplished through a simple averaging of lamina or interface stresses or strains over a critical distance, or taking stress or strain at a critical distance from the stress concentration point, prior to substitution in the failure equations presented.

3.0 MATERIAL ALLOWABLES

One important factor in the ability of the failure criterion just presented to reliably predict failure depends upon the accuracy of the material allowables. From Equations 1 and 3, it can be observed that only five material allowables are required (σ_{1ta} , σ_{1ca} , σ_{2ta} , σ_{2ca} , and τ_{12sa}) if the relationship,

derived from application of the failure criterion to compression tests of 90° coupons, of $0.5\sigma_{2ca} = \tau_{23sa}$ is used. As was previously mentioned, the structures under consideration are cylinders. Considerable evidence exists that material properties derived from flat coupon tests don't translate well into material allowables for curved structures without utilizing some unknown knockdown factors. As a result, a series of implosion and explosion ring and JANNAF tube tests (Figure 3) are suggested in order to determine material allowables for cylinder type structures. Since the same fabrication procedures would be used for the rings, tubes and cylinders, the resulting material tests should accurately establish the material allowables for use in the failure criterion equations.

4.0 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

The application of any failure criterion demands an accurate stress/strain analysis. With composite materials, the level of microstructure at which the analysis is performed is an additional consideration. For example, the stress analysis can be conducted at the micro-level where individual fibers and the surrounding matrix are modeled, the lamina or ply-by-ply level where each ply is represented as an individual homogeneous orthotropic material, or the laminate level where the laminate is treated as a homogeneous anisotropic material by "smearing" individual ply properties. Finite element analysis of a sizeable structure below the laminate level of microstructure will, in general, require the application of global/local analysis techniques. A trade off exists in the choice of microstructural level of analysis between accuracy and practicality. Although an analysis at the laminate level requires a substantially less refined finite element grid than one at the ply-by-ply level, individual ply stresses are more difficult to recover and are less accurately determined.

5.0 EXAMPLES

5.1 Double Notched Shear Cylindrical Test Specimen (DNS)

The DNS specimen shown in Figure 4 was fiber placed and in-situ consolidated with AS4/APC-2 by ICI Composite Structures for the purpose of studying the strength of the interfaces with different surface preparations. The modified Hashin's failure criterion was tested out on this DNS specimen. Two finite element models were utilized: one with smeared 3D properties used for the outer cylinder and a fine mesh, 0.51mm by 0.63mm, (0.02 inches by 0.025 inches), and one with hoop and axial 3D properties and an ultrafine mesh, 0.20mm by 0.51mm (0.008 inches by 0.020 inches). Since the recommended ring and tube tests had not been performed to obtain the material allowables, flat coupon test specimen values were modified with a manufacturing process knockdown and a statistical knockdown. The resulting material allowables are given in Table 1. ABAQUS four noded axisymmetric 2D solid finite elements with 3D material properties and reduced integration were used. A close-up of the meshes in the critical region is shown in Figures 5a and 5b. Using the strains at the integration points to compute the ply stresses and strains at the experimentally observed failure load and substituting into Equations 1 and 3, the values of the various failure functions are given in Table 2 for the hoop, axial and hull lay-ups of the inner and outer cylinders respectively. The results show that a matrix failure would have been predicted to occur at the actual failure load in the lower notch region of the inner cylinder with both meshes. The actual DNS specimen did fail in the lower notch area. The critical distance in the fine mesh is 0.25mm (0.01 inches) and 0.10mm (0.004 inches) in the ultrafine mesh.

5.2 Sixty One Centimeter (24 Inch) Diameter Cylindrical I Frames

The two 61cm (24 inch) diameter I frames shown in Figure 6 were fabricated with AS4/APC-2 by co-consolidating back to back quasi-isotropic thermoformed channel segments along with an in-situ consolidated all hoop ply inner ring, and then overwrapping with in-situ consolidated hoop and hull lay-ups. The frames were then tested in a fixture which applies a uniform external radial pressure. This test evaluates the strength of the frame and its interfaces in the circumferential direction. The two frames were evaluated using the modified Hashin's criterion for the meshes given in Figure 7, and the properties and allowables in Table 1. The predicted failure loads were 24.4 MPa (3,541 psi) and 30.1 MPa (4,363 psi) respectively for the trial and test frames. The actual failure loads were 20.6 MPa (2,951 psi) and 20.3 MPa (2,986 psi) respectively. The values of the failure functions computed at the failure loads using the modified Hashin's criterion are

shown in Table 3. In this example the modified Hashin's criterion predicted a much higher failure load than the actual failure load. However, a total of eight back to back quasi-isotropic channel sections were used in the frame fabrication. This resulted in a total of 8 splice joints in the web. At the web splices (load discontinuity), the strain gages showed that hoop strains were approximately twice as high as the areas away from the splice. Therefore the axisymmetric analyses used were inadequate for the failure prediction in the splice regions. 3D solid analyses of the splice joint are planned to better establish the actual 3D stress state. Had there been no splice joints, a considerably high load could have been reached.

6.0 SUMMARY/CONCLUSIONS

A physically based 3D composite failure criterion has been presented along with its application to two test cases. In the first example of the DNS specimen the modified Hashin's failure criterion was reasonably successful in predicting failure. In that case the actual failure and predicted failure was in the matrix in the lower notch region. In the second example with 61cm (24 inch) diameter test frames the primary mode of failure was compressive fiber failure, and the modified Hashin's failure criterion over predicted the failure load. However, the lack of correlation between the test and the theory is thought to result from the fact that the splice joint introduced a stress riser which was not accounted for in the axisymmetric analysis. Further work is planned to answer the questions on the splice effect, but the initial results presented here are promising and offer a viable, convenient, failure criterion for thick composites.

7.0 REFERENCES

1. Hashin, Z., *Failure Criteria for Unidirectional Fiber Composites*, Journal Applied Mechanics, June 1980, pp. 329-334.
2. Whitney, J. M. and Nuismer, R. J., *Stress Fracture Criteria for Laminated Composites Containing Stress Concentrations*, Journal Composite Materials, July 1974, pp. 253-265.
3. Hibbit, Karlsson & Sorensen, Inc., ABAQUS Version 4.9, General Finite Element Program, Providence, RI.

8.0 NOMENCLATURE

β	=	Angle of Plane Parallel to Fiber Direction
σ_1	=	Stress in Fiber Direction
$\sigma_{2,3}$	=	Stresses Transverse to Fiber Direction
σ_n	=	Normal Stress on β Plane
τ_{nt}, τ_{nl}	=	Shear Stresses on β Plane
τ_{ij}	=	Shear Stresses
σ_{ica}	=	Compression Stress Allowable in i Direction
σ_{ita}	=	Tension Stress Allowable in i Direction
τ_{ijsa}	=	Shear Stress Allowable
F_t	=	Tension Failure Function
F_c	=	Compression Failure Function

Table 1 - AS4/APC-2 Material Properties and Allowables

Lamina Properties		Lamina Allowables			
E ₁	110.24 GPa (16.00 Msi)	σ_{1ta}	1,560 MPa (228.0 Ksi)	ϵ_{1ta}	0.01140 (mm/mm)
E ₂	9.99 GPa (1.45 Msi)	σ_{2ta}	66.1 MPa (9.6 Ksi)	ϵ_{2ta}	0.00665 (mm/mm)
E ₃	9.99 GPa (1.45 Msi)	σ_{1ca}	-726.9 MPa (-105.5 Ksi)	ϵ_{1ca}	-0.00660 (mm/mm)
ν_{12}	0.33	σ_{2ca}	-177.1 MPa (-25.7 Ksi)	ϵ_{2ca}	-0.01737 (mm/mm)
ν_{13}	0.33	τ_{23ta}	79.2 MPa (11.5 Ksi)	ϵ_{23ta}	0.02501 (mm/mm)
ν_{23}	0.45	τ_{12sa}	74.4 MPa (10.8 Ksi)	ϵ_{12sa}	0.01555 (mm/mm)
G ₂₃	3.79 GPa (0.55 Msi)	τ_{13sa}	74.4 MPa (10.8 Ksi)	ϵ_{13sa}	0.01555 (mm/mm)
G ₁₂	5.72 GPa (0.83 Msi)				
G ₁₃	5.72 GPa (0.83 Msi)				

Table 2 - Failure Functions for Double Notched Shear Cylindrical Test Specimen

Location	Lay-Up	FINE MESH		ULTRAFINE MESH	
		Fiber Failure (Eq. 1)	Matrix Failure (Eq. 3)	Fiber Failure (Eq. 1)	Matrix Failure (Eq. 3)
Inner Cylinder	Axial	0.736	0.307	0.768	0.289
	Hoop	0.277	0.989	0.280	1.063
Outer Cylinder	Hull	0.864	0.818	0.851	1.000

Table 3 - Failure Functions for 61 cm (24 inch) Diameter Cylindrical I Frames

Location	Lay-Up	TRIAL FRAME 20.33 MPa (2951 Psi)		TEST FRAME 20.59 MPa (2986 Psi)	
		Fiber Failure (Eq. 1)	Matrix Failure (Eq. 3)	Fiber Failure (Eq. 1)	Matrix Failure (Eq. 3)
Hull	90 ₂ /0	-	-	0.594	0.206
Flange	Hoop	0.726	0.833	0.639	0.684
Flange/Web	Quasi	0.772	0.439	0.679	0.536

Figure 1 - Hashin's Two Modes of Failure in a Composite Ply

Figure 2 - Matrix Failure Plane and β Angle

Figure 3 - Material Allowable Tests

Figure 4 - Double Notched Shear Cylindrical Test Specimen

Figure 5 - Axisymmetric Finite Element Meshes For DNS Test Specimens

- (a) Fine Mesh of Lower Notch Area (b) Ultrafine Mesh of Lower Notch Area

Figure 6 - 61 cm (24 in) Outer Diameter Cylinder Test Frames

Figure 7 - Axisymmetric Finite Element Meshes for 61 cm (24in) Frames

